

METHODS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Annotation: The content of this article is dedicated to games that develop the professional competencies of future music teachers. Didactic game methods contribute to a solid assimilation of educational material, broaden horizons, develop creative thinking, artistic imagination, memory, observation, intuition.

Key words: Didactic games, variational method, adaptive method, heuristic method, identification, protection methods, "Theatrical games", "Bewitched boy".

Nowadays, a rich treasure of teaching methods has been collected in the musical education system. If we can properly use pedagogical technologies in the development of musical education, we can achieve the intended result with confidence and in a short way. The continuous development of research in the field of educational technologies and the emergence of new opportunities, the successful implementation of musical education tasks require constant updating of music teaching methods, creative use of music pedagogy, especially general pedagogy.

The analysis of the games shows that it is correct to use the following games before the university and in the initial period of the university. These are cases related to representative professional activity:

variant method - this activity includes tasks aimed at choosing an option, handling, studying the work of the teacher and solving the main issues;

method of adaptation - consists of using a method of solving a specific problem, and this method will have to be adapted to a specific musical pedagogical activity at the end of the work;

heuristic method - an independent and new approach to the problem.

For example, methodical analysis of the teaching process; creating an alternative plan; receiving information, understanding, developing trust in the outside world; increase self-esteem; improvement of working conditions based on the assessment given to him. Finding a solution to every innovation. In such cases, a person self-confidence gives good results and shyness disappears.

The teacher is one of those who accept the incoming news and apply it to his life. The teacher should be an innovator in changing his activities. The psychological system has its own mechanism, that is, identification. Identity is the uniqueness of human experience. Therefore, every teacher is considered to be an innovator who introduces and develops new things. When he receives the news, he turns its result for the better and implements it.

When considering each method of psychology, different conclusions are reached.

Protection methods

The anti-pedagogical barrier is the value in literature, the application of custom in life, the teacher's understanding of his identity. The methods of its reception are described as follows:

1. For example, we have a new idea. What is new in this idea, how is it with the old similarity is compared;
2. This we cannot do. Why? Because we deserve a positive answer to the negative rely on not having a base;
3. This news does not lead to any changes. Divide into groups there is an opinion that the effect of teaching does not lead to change;
4. This innovation requires additional processing. Deficiencies in work experience will be developed;
5. This news is not much different from the old one;
6. If there are ways to enter additional information, it will be entered.

Getting acquainted with the changes introduced by other schools to this innovation in the experiment. The methodology of applying this innovation to the working conditions will be developed:

1. Development of a document about news;
2. Separate illumination of the desired side;
3. Use as an experiment;
4. Discussion of the negative method;
5. Compare both results.

A person's fear of news will have a negative effect. These are obstacles that affect the pedagogue in implementing his chosen method.

Such researches show that in the modeling of the mental game, educational activity turns into creative educational activity.

Game modeling expands the scope of the child's thinking and has a positive effect on his future activities.

"Let's decide - rate" game

Parallel groups take part in the game. In the first group, the teacher creates a problem situation, the students offer their solutions. Proposals are recorded on a tape recorder. In the process of writing, the teacher examines the suggestions. The issue will be resolved through discussion.

A similar situation is created in the second group. Students try to solve this problem. The teacher told them: "Earlier, they tried to solve this problem in the first group as well. "If you analyze how well they made the right decision, because today you are also solving this problem," he says. They analyze the thoughts written on the magnetic tape. The decision will be confirmed. The purpose of this is to find out the students' activity and thinking.

During didactic games, the educational process is organized as follows. That is, creating a problematic situation, determining the direction of the game, summing up the points and evaluating the students themselves.

Imitation modeling games also play a big role in the development of future music teachers. Such games create problematic pedagogical situations. Theatricalization of games, pedagogues can also take part in it. These games help in mastering specific knowledge.

Exercise games were used in the first stage of the experimental work process. Because they help to increase attention, strengthen memory and imagination. At this stage, all the games were played as a team, because fear may appear in the child when he is in front of the audience.

Little by little, we started doing individual tasks. In the second stage, a little more complicated tasks are carried out. With the help of such tasks, the teacher's attitude to his profession is determined. For example: "Who is right?", "How to help?", "Conversation in the teacher's room" etc. Such discussions teach how to "see the problem" in the current situation. And it finds several solutions.

"Theatrical Games"

Theatrical games are full of emotions and at the same time they need additional analysis. Accordingly, in order to solve the problem, future music teachers are given the following tasks: "Protect your teacher". In this, the teachers' characters and their work methods are analyzed. "Two characters are compared" and so on.

"Enchanted Child"

A special place is given to the concept of interaction in these games. At this stage, it is taken into account "reading from the person's face", that is, understanding his emotions based on his facial expressions. The name of this game is "Enchanted Boy". The analysis of such experiences showed that: during the game activity, future music teachers have the ability to independently solve various problems. This stage can be called sensitive. It is at this stage that the teacher is fully formed, attentive to others, open-minded and begins to approach pedagogical issues at a professional level. In the course of these stages of learning, he becomes a perfect person, a student with a high level of knowledge. For this, it is necessary to use the technology of personality formation.

Below, we will get acquainted with the didactic games held with high school students and first-year students.

"Press conference" game

Before this game, the participants are divided into 2 groups:

Group 1: reporters, presenters of various newspapers, magazines, radio and television programs;

Group 2: "scientists", "musicologists", "instrumentalists", "methodologists" and others.

Each group performs its own task, that is, gets acquainted with materials consisting of new topics in different positions. A group of "reporters" prepares for an interview. They make a general plan and questions for the interview. The second group uses educational material and additional materials that help to participate in the name of "scientists", "musicologists" and others.

At the meeting held before the game, the groups choose the students who will participate in the game, agree on the questions to be used.

During the training, the "Reporter" group "scientists", "musicologists",

They interview "musicians", "stylists" and others. They express their personal opinions and assumptions.

The rest evaluate the game and express their additional opinions.

"Travel" game

Before the game, the members of the jury are determined and the children are divided into several groups. There are 5-6 children in each group, and a captain is appointed for each group. The participants of the game conditionally "travel" to different musical disciplines and perform various tasks.

Each captain selects one envelope. It will have one main question and two additional questions. After answering them, the next step will be taken. The goal of each group is one, that is, to "travel" many subjects and solve problems on all subjects.

Answers are evaluated according to the established system. It takes into account problem solving skills and team management. At the end of the trip, the members of the committee will conclude.

"Erudit" game

After completing several topics, one question that creates a problematic situation on these topics is written, written on a card, and distributed to the jury members. The committee members will consist of 2-3 people. The most interesting questions (out of 10-12 questionnaires) will be determined together with the members of the jury. Before the start of the game, the cards are sorted on the table. One participant from each group chooses 4 questions for his group. After that, they will be given time to prepare. Each group works together to solve the problem. If the question is more complicated, another card is given. However, it will be taken into account in the final evaluation. At the end of the game, the jury members will announce the scores based on the answers and independently prepared questions.

"Accompaniment" game

Groups are divided into 3-4 problem "laboratories". Part of the scientific news given on the problem is given orally. All additional information about the problem, students to the teacher they find out by asking questions. The answers are discussed among the members of the "laboratory". After the discussion of the received information, the participants determine the solution to the problem. Then one person from each "lab".

He gives his option regarding the solution of the problem. After that, each group will prove its solution. If there are those who wish, they will add to this problem and express their opinions. The ideas of the groups are discussed and evaluated.

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